

ACTION OF FUMING NITRIC ACID ON IODINE.

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Iodine pentoxide is the product obtained by the interaction of iodine and fuming nitric acid, under ordinary conditions. By removing the oxides of nitrogen from the original yellow powder, in the absence of moisture, iodine dioxide is also formed.

Millon (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1844, 12, 330, 345, 353; *J. pr. Chem.*, 1845, 34, 321) has described the preparation of iodine dioxide by the action of very concentrated nitric acid on iodine. Bahl and Partington (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1258) have, however, found that iodine when reacted upon by nitric acid (*d* 1.5) gives iodine pentoxide, a result which agrees with that of Guichard (*Compt. rend.*, 1909, 148, 1923; *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1909, 5, 86) who obtained a better yield by using nitric anhydride.

Moles and Villan (*Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1936, 34, 787) found that the product of this reaction was iodine dioxide, I_2O_4 , mixed with free nitric acid.

These conflicting observations have necessitated a revision of this investigation of the action of nitric acid on iodine. It has been found, as stated by Bahl and Partington (*loc. cit.*), that by triturating iodine with fuming nitric acid and drying the product under ordinary conditions, iodine pentoxide is obtained. Analytical results are given in the experimental part.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Iodine was determined by the reduction with sulphur dioxide and precipitation of silver iodide in the presence of nitric acid. Oxygen was estimated as described by Bahl and Partington (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1088).

TABLE I.

Sample.	Iodine.	Oxygen.
A	75.98 %	23.70 %
B	75.50	23.80
C	75.52	23.65

These results show that the product is mainly iodine pentoxide, I_2O_5 (Calc. I, 76.04%; O, 23.96%).

By modifying the conditions of the experiment it was, however, found possible to prepare appreciable quantities of iodine dioxide, I_2O_4 . This was done by removing the oxides of nitrogen by passing dry air through the iodine oxide contained in a glass Gooch sinter. The last traces of the nitrogen oxides were absorbed by solid caustic potash in a desiccator. The atmosphere in the latter was kept dry by placing some phosphorus pentoxide inside it. Low temperature gives a better yield, so the desiccator was kept cool in the ice-cold water. The dry product thus obtained was washed with water, alcohol and ether respectively over a suction pump. It was finally dried over phosphorus pentoxide in a desiccator. The product was analysed as before and the results are recorded below.

TABLE II.

Sample.	Iodine.	Oxygen.
A	79.50 %	20.20 %
B	79.29	20.09
C	79.40	20.16
D	79.17	20.02

(I_2O_4 requires I, 79.88% ; O, 20.12%).

It was noticed that the yellow voluminous powder, obtained by triturating iodine with fuming nitric acid, decomposed on exposure to give the brown iodine pentoxide. This decomposition is brought about by two factors, *viz.*, (i) heat and (ii) moisture.

The latter factor had a greater influence on the decomposition of iodine dioxide in the presence of the fumes of the oxides of nitrogen due to the generation of heat, produced by the absorption of moisture by the fumes of the oxides of nitrogen. This view was confirmed by the addition of a drop of water to a freshly prepared yellow powder before removal of the oxides of nitrogen, when the whole mass rapidly turned brown.

This decomposition can, to a very great extent, be prevented by removing the oxides of nitrogen in complete absence of moisture.

It is clear, therefore, that the primary product of the interaction of iodine and fuming nitric acid is iodine dioxide, I_2O_4 , which in contact with moisture decomposes into iodine pentoxide and iodine, which colours the product brown.